

Effectiveness of Structured Teaching Programme on Knowledge Regarding National Nutrition Mission (POSHAN ABHIYAAN) among Mothers in Selected Community Area of Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh

Indra Bamrel, Bsc 4th Year, Sharda School of Nursing Science and Research, Sharda University, Greater Noida
 Divya Upreti, , Assistant Professor, Sharda School of Nursing Science and Research, Sharda University, Greater Noida
 Ankita Chikara, Senior Tutor, Sharda School of Nursing Science and Research, Sharda University, Greater Noida
 Ayushi Saini, Bsc 4th Year, Sharda School of Nursing Science and Research, Sharda University, Greater Noida

Corresponding author: Ms. Divya Upreti, ,Assistant Professor, Sharda School of Nursing Science and Research, Sharda University, Greater Noida

Abstract:- Public Sustenance Mission or Poshan Abhiyaan intends to work on the nourishing wellbeing of kids, young people, lactating moms and pregnant ladies. The Public Nourishment Mission is India's leader program pointed toward working on the wholesome status of youths, youngsters, pregnant ladies, and lactating moms. It is upheld by the NITI Aayog's Public Sustenance System, which intends to accomplish "KuPoshan Mukt Bharat," or hunger free India, by 2022. Hindering, undernutrition, pallor (among small kids, ladies, and young adult young ladies), and low birth weight will be diminished by 2%, 2%, 3%, and 2% consistently, separately. In a mission mode, address the issue of unhealthiness. descriptive study carried out among 100 women of panchayatan , Greater Noida. Convenience sampling technique was used. The data was collected through a self-organized information Survey and 5-point Likert disposition scale to evaluate information and demeanor in regards to utilization of Public Nourishing mission. Anindita, et al. (2015) led an observational cross sectional concentrate on appraisal of the information, mentality and genuine acts of breastfeeding in the 286 moms of kids matured under 2 years who went to the Vaccination facility of Greetings Tech Clinical School and Medical clinic, Bhubaneswar, in Odisha, India. Information on commencement of breastfeeding inside 30 minutes to one hour of birth was there in 52.78% moms and 40% had a thought regarding the significance of colostrums. The importance of restrictive breastfeeding was known to 34.97% while practically 48% moms started breastfeeding inside thirty minutes of birth, 75% took care of colostrums to their babies, 61% were rehearsing selective breastfeeding for initial a half year and 90% were rehearsing night takes care of. Improper connection and situating was seen in 55% of moms. Just 15% began weaning (beneficial taking care of) following a half year of child's age. Yadav (2016) directed an unmistakable report on the information and

works on with respect to Counteraction of Protein Energy Hunger among 100 moms of under-five youngsters at the chose area of Gajipur, New Delhi. The outcomes uncovered that the greater part, 45.36 percent of moms had information connected with general data of PEM, trailed by 43.44 percent of the moms who had some awareness of causes, signs and side effects of PEM. A larger part of 46.3% of the respondents had the right dietary practice and 42 percent of moms had the great act of the board of loose bowels. There is critical affiliation seen between the information and instructive status of the mother. Generally speaking discoveries showed existing, information and practice as observed to be 45.52% and 41.66% in the avoidance of protein energy lack of healthy sustenance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Mission POSHAN2.0 is an Incorporated Nourishment Backing System. It tries to address the difficulties of unhealthiness in kids, juvenile young ladies, pregnant ladies and lactating maters through an essential change in sustenance content and conveyance and by making of a coincident Eco-framework to create and advance practices that support wellbeing, goodness and exemption. Poshan2.0 will look to enhance the quality and conveyance of food under the Beneficial Sustenance Program.

Mission Poshan2.0 will add to mortal capital improvement of the country; address ailing health challenges; advance sustenance care and great dietary patterns for manageable wellbeing and prosperity and address nourishment related shortcomings through essential systems. Under the program, nutritive ethics and standards and quality and testing of THR will be bettered and lesser partner and devisee investment will be advanced other than conventional local area food propensities. Poshan2.0 will bring 3 significant projects

plans under its dimension, viz., Anganwadi Administrations, Plan for Juvenile Young ladies and Poshan Abhiyaan.

Poshan2.0 will focus on nurturing Sustenance, youngster and energetic Kid Taking care of ethics, Treatment of MAM/SAM and Wellbeing through AYUSH. It'll lay on the mainstays of Union, Administration, and Limit structure. Poshan Abhiyan will be the critical point of support for Effort and will cover creations connected with nutritive help, ICT intercessions, Media Backing and Exploration, People group Effort and Jan Andolan. Mission Poshan2.0 will incorporate a few essential methodologies to satisfy its objects, viz., Restorative methodologies, Nourishment care procedures, Correspondence techniques and Making of greeneco-frameworks. The articles under Mission Poshan2.0 will be acknowledged areas of strength for through driven incidental molding with essential Services/Depts./Affiliations. Computerized structure under the " Poshan Tracker " carried out by MoWCD on first Walk 2021 through Nationale-Administration Division as an administration device, will fortify and achieve clarity in nourishment conveyance emotionally supportive networks. Innovation under Poshan Tracker is being mishandled for(I) dynamic distinguishing proof of stifling, squandering, under-weight frequency among kids;(ii) last far off shadowing of nourishment administration conveyance.

➤ Objectives

- To assess the knowledge regarding awareness about National Nutrition Mission (Poshan Abhiyaan) Among Mothers in Selected Community Areas of Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh.
- To assess the practice regarding utilization about National Nutrition Mission (Poshan Abhiyaan) Among Mothers.
- To figure out the relationship between the information with respect to Public Sustenance Mission Among Moms and chose segment factors.

➤ Assumption

- Women may have some knowledge regarding National Nutritional Mission
- The knowledge regarding National Nutritional mission may vary with the selected Demographic variables among at Panchayatan village

➤ Operational Definitions

- Assess- It refers to the critical analysis and evaluation of judgement of the status where the women's knowledge on National Nutritional mission.
- Knowledge- Familiarity or awareness about the National Nutritional mission among women of Panchayatan village up Greater Noida
- Attitude- Attitude refers to settled thinking or feeling of the women regarding importance of national nutritional mission

- National nutritional mission- It is a leader program to work on the dietary results for kids, pregnant ladies, and lactating moms in India and is likewise called the Public Nourishment Mission

➤ Inclusion Criteria

- Panchayatan village : women of panchayat village
- Those who want to participate willingly.

➤ Exclusion Criteria

- Panchayatan village women those are not easily accessible.
- The study was delimited to the women and lactating women of all ages

II. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table 1 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of sample Characteristics (N=100)

Demographic variables	N	%
1. Age in years		
a. 22-25	29	29.0
b. 26-35	26	26.0
c. 36-55	23	23.0
d. 56 and above	22	22
2. Religion		
a. Hindu	63	63.0
b. Muslim	25	25.0
c. Christian	5	5.0
d. Others	7	7.0
3. Occupational status of Mothers		
a. Household work	50	50.0
b. Farmer	30	30.0
c. Govt. Job	17	17.0
d. Business	3	3.0
4. Educational status of Mothers		
a. No formal education	46	46.0
b. Primary education	28	28.0
c. Secondary education	19	19.0
d. Higher education	6	6.0
5 Family Monthly Income		
a. <5000	9	9.0
b. 5000-20000	36	36.0
c. 20001-40000	37	37.0
d. >40000	18	18.0
6. Type of family		
a. Joint	28	28.0

b. Nuclear	36	36.0
c. Extended family	26	26.0
d. Single parent	10	10.0
7.Type of diet		
a. Vegetarian	49	29.0
b. Mixed	51	26.0
8. Do you know about malnutrition		
a. Yes	53	53.0
b. No	47	47.0
9. Source of information		
a. Newspaper and Magazines	34	34.0
b. TV/Radio	33	33.0
c. Friends or relatives	18	18.0
d. Others	15	15.0

Table 1 shows that majority (29.0%) of them were in age group of 22-25 years, most (63.0%) them were Hindus, majority (50.0%) the participants were doing household work, most (46.0%) them had no formal education, majority (37.0%) of them had family income of 20,001-40,000, most (36.0%) of

them belongs to nuclear family, majority (51.0%) of them had mixed dietary pattern, most (53.0%) of them knew about malnutrition and majority (34.0%) of them had source of information through newspapers/magazines.

Table 2 ,Frequency &Percentage Distribution of sample based on level of knowledge during pre-test &post-test (N=100)

Knowledge level	Pre-test		Post-test	
	n	%	N	%
Poor	63	63.0	16	16.0
Average	37	37.0	59	59.0
Good	0	0.0	25	25.0

The information introduced in table 2 shows that, during pre-test greater part (63.0%) of the example have unfortunate degree of information, 37.0 % of them have normal degree of information, and none (0%) of them have great degree of information and during post-test larger part (59.0%) of them have normal degree of information, around 16.0 % of them have unfortunate degree of information and 25.0% of them have Great degree of information

Table 3 Comparison of knowledge scores among sample inpre-test and post-test (N=100)

Knowledge	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean difference	Paired-test	P value
Pre-test	6.84	2.42	4.52	12.92	0.001 (S)
Post-test	11.34	4.20			

(p<0.05 significant level) S- Significant and NS-Non Significant

It reveals that, there was a measurably massive distinction noted in the mean scores of information at p<0.001 among pre and post-test among test. It shows that the mediation was powerful in working on the information. Thus scientist neglected to acknowledge invalid speculation (H01).

Table 4 Association between level ofknowledge with demographicvariables during post-test (N=100)

Demographic variables	Level of Knowledge						Chi-square test (χ^2) & p value
	Poor		Average		Good		
	n	%	n	n	%	n	
1.Age in years							$\chi^2=8.77$ p=0.18 (NS)
a. 22-25	2	12.5	21	35.6	6	24.0	
b. 26-35	8	50.0	13	22.0	5	20.0	
c. 36-55	4	25.0	13	22.0	6	24.0	
d. 56 and above	2	12.5	12	20.3	8	32.0	
2. Religion							$\chi^2=13.29$ p=0.03 (S)
a. Hindu	11	68.8	43	72.9	9	36.0	
b. Muslim	3	18.8	11	18.6	11	44.0	
c. Christian	0	5.0	2	3.4	3	12.0	

d. Others	2	12.5	3	5.1	2	8.0	$\chi^2=2.59$ p=0.85 (NS)
3. Occupational status of Mothers							
a. Household work	7	43.8	32	54.2	11	44.0	
b. Farmer	5	31.2	16	27.1	9	36.0	
c. Govt. Job	3	18.8	9	15.3	5	20.0	
d. Business	1	6.2	2	3.4	0	0.0	
4. Educational status of Mothers							$\chi^2=7.04$ p=0.53 (NS)
a. No formal education	5	31.2	29	49.2	12	48.0	
b. Primary education	6	37.5	12	20.3	10	40.0	
c. Secondary education	4	25.0	13	22.0	2	8.0	
d. Higher education	1	6.2	4	6.8	1	4.0	
5. Family Monthly Income							$\chi^2=8.72$ p=0.19 (NS)
a. <5000	0	0.0	6	10.2	3	12.0	
b. 5000-20000	10	62.5	20	33.9	6	24.0	
c. 20001-40000	4	25.0	24	40.7	9	36.0	
d. >40000	2	12.5	9	15.3	7	28.0	
6. Type of family							$\chi^2=8.95$ p=0.17 (NS)
a. Joint	8	50.0	15	25.4	5	20.0	
b. Nuclear	3	18.8	25	42.4	8	32.0	
c. Extended family	5	31.2	13	22.0	8	32.0	
d. Single parent	0	0.0	6	10.2	4	16.0	
7.Type of diet							$\chi^2=1.63$ p=0.44 (NS)
a. Vegetarian	7	43.8	32	54.2	10	40.0	
b. Mixed	9	56.2	27	45.8	15	60.0	
8. Do you know about malnutrition							$\chi^2=8.09$ p=0.23 (NS)
a. Yes	9	56.2	28	47.5	16	64.0	
b. No	7	33.8	31	52.6	9	36.0	
9. Source of information							$\chi^2=1.63$ p=0.44 (NS)
a. Newspaper and Magazines	5	31.2	19	32.2	10	40.0	
b. TV/Radio	5	31.2	19	32.2	9	36.0	
c. Friends or relatives	6	37.5	9	15.3	3	12.0	
d. Others	0	0.0	12	20.3	3	12.0	

($p < 0.05$ significant level) S- Significant and NS-Non Significant

The information introduced hotel table 4 uncovered that, there is no huge relationship between level of information with segment factors of test during post-test. Chi-square test was processed to track down the huge affiliation. It uncovers that there was genuinely huge ($p > 0.05$) affiliation tracked down between level of information with segment factors except for religion ($p < 0.05$).

III. LIMITATIONS

- The study is limited to selected women and child of Panchayatan village up, Greater Noida UP.
- Women of Panchayatan village who wants to participate.

- All women who are not present on day of the data collection.

IV. RECOMMENDATION FOR FURTHER STUDY

- A similar can be done on large sample to validate and generalize the findings
- A similar study can be done for other innovative nutritional program.
- Similar study can be conducted and evaluated using teaching strategies like structural teaching program.
- A similar study can be done on mothers.

V. CONCLUSION

It has been concluded from this study that even literate and qualified people from panchayat an village have lack of knowledge about National Nutritional mission. But a little bit of knowledge about National Nutritional mission can enhance their knowledge and attitude towards National Nutritional mission

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